

Role of Patient Specific Implant in Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery: A Review

Asmita Sharma¹
 Parityancha Bansal²
 Gursimrat Brar³
 Ramandeep Singh Brar⁴
 Jasbinder Kumar⁵

PG Student¹
 Department of Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery
 Dasmesh Institute of Research & Dental Sciences
 Faridkot, Punjab, India

PG Student²
 Department of Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery
 Dasmesh Institute of Research & Dental Sciences
 Faridkot, Punjab, India

Professor³
 Department of Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery
 Dasmesh Institute of Research & Dental Sciences
 Faridkot, Punjab, India

Professor & HOD⁴
 Department of Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery
 Dasmesh Institute of Research & Dental Sciences
 Faridkot, Punjab, India

Assistant Professor⁵
 Department of Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery
 Dasmesh Institute of Research & Dental Sciences
 Faridkot, Punjab, India

Abstract

Maxillofacial reconstructive surgeries of acquired or congenital defects in this era where the aesthetic concerns of patients are very high is considered as a challenge for any surgeon. Modern alternatives for creating patient specific implants (PSIs) with increased accuracy have given a fresh and improved outlook in many maxillofacial defects like reconstruction of TMJ, orbital floor, orthognathic or mandibular defects. The purpose of this review is to present a comprehensive summary of the existing scientific knowledge of PSI and describe its current and future applications in maxillofacial surgery.

Keywords: Patient Specific Implant, Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, PEEK.

Introduction

Even the most skilled surgeon may find reconstructive surgery to be quite difficult because of the intricate anatomy, delicate systems involved, and individuality of each lesion. And in order to improve the outcome of patient, it is imperative to restore the defect in the best possible way along with improving the amount of time needed for the surgical process.⁽¹⁾ In such cases, a patient specific implant (PSI) that is made to fit precisely into the anatomical abnormalities or anomalies may be an effective option. In the field of medicine, the necessity to create PSI has led to numerous breakthroughs and technical advancements.⁽²⁾ In this review article, we aim to provide a comprehensive overview of the diverse applic

-ations of PSI in OMFS by analyzing recent advancements, challenges, and future prospects.

Material Used

Over the past years, a variety of implant materials have been refined to restore damaged soft and hard tissue structures for PSI. The ideal implant material that is to be used should be radiolucent, biocompatible with tissues, lightweight, and have features that make it easy to modify. The morbidity donor site is one of the drawbacks associated with the use of autologous grafts, although this is not an issue because these materials are plentiful. These implants have been largely discussed in the flowchart mentioned below: (Flowchart 1)⁽³⁾

(Flowchart 1)

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PDLLA and PLGA are two absorbable polymers that are frequently used in paediatric craniofacial surgeries. However, it is possible for foreign body reactions to arise after implant therapy, and reports of material breakage have also been made in few situations.

In order to facilitate bone tissue engineering, hydroxyapatite (HA) has been used as a biocompatible scaffold. They have a significant capacity to cling to the bone and soft tissues, and they are non-resorbable and osteoconductive by nature.

Due to their desirable properties, such as higher mechanical strength and better resistance to friction, metallic implants have been widely used for both permanent and temporary prosthesis, such as dental implants or screws. However, because of their high strength and elastic modulus, which are not comparable to normal human bone, they create a stress shielding effect that causes the prosthesis to loosen.⁽⁴⁾

The least harmful materials are ceramics, which also mix quite well with bodily tissues. However, they are not appropriate for load bearing applications due to their decreased ductility and fracture toughness, as well as their higher elasticity modulus and brittleness.⁽⁵⁾

Polyether ether ketone (PEEK) has become a promising alloplastic material that could be employed as a workable substitute in the creation of patient-specific implants (PSI) due to recent developments in technology and material production. It is renowned for having a lower infection rate, increased resilience, and endurance to changes in the environment. Numerous researches on PEEK utilization have been done, detailing the benefits and the difficulties encountered when utilizing PEEK prostheses.⁽⁶⁾

To overcome these problems Porous polyethylene (PPE) and ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMW-PE) are two types of polyethylene that are used in the treatment of orbital deformities and facial development. PPE is easy to model, long-lasting, and allows for tissue ingrowth through its pores. However, there is a probability that infection will happen. Because of its solid structure, UHMW-PE is used to fabricate PSIs utilising CAD-CAM technology for the rehabilitation of temporomandibular or orbital joints. When compared to PPE, UHMW-PE is said to have a reduced incidence of infection rate.⁽⁷⁾

Work Flow

Using computed tomography/magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) 2D image data as digital imaging and communications in medicine (DICOM) files, the manufacturing process starts with the image acquisition. Since a 3D printer cannot interpret DICOM images, these DICOM files are then ready to be used with software (3D Doctor, MIMICS) to create a 3D model of the anatomical abnormality. For the 3D printer to interpret the DICOM images, they must be converted to a Surface file (STL file). The necessary software programmes for generating STL files and processing DICOM data are: (Figure 1)⁽¹⁾

- Mimics Innovation Suite- paid
- Vitrea- Open Source
- Osirix- Open source
- Mesh Mixer- Open source

(Figure 1)

(Flowchart 2)

Manufacturing Techniques

Manufacturing of this data in 3D shape for it to come to life can be done in following ways (Flowchart 2).

Previously, these patient-specific implants were made by subtractive manufacturing, in which material was cut into the desired shape by slicing off sections. Nevertheless, it was observed that a significant amount of material was wasted and that computer numerical control (CNC) could not accurately recreate complex anatomical structures. This made it possible to produce implants tailored to each patient through additive manufacturing, also referred to as rapid prototyping or 3D printing. In addition to overcoming subtractive manufacturing's drawbacks, this sped up the creation of these patient-specific implants. Using digitally controlled and operated material laying tools, AM builds a model from the ground up and deposits the material layer by layer. Layer-by-layer construction gives manufacturers of complicated products an unprecedented degree of flexibility.⁽⁸⁾

Mirroring

For craniofacial surgeons, exact symmetric repair of maxillofacial abnormalities is still an unresolved issue in the great majority of instances. The optimal prosthesis for reestablishing facial symmetry can now be created by preoperatively

"mirroring" the surgery using the healthy side as a template, thanks to the advancement of computational technologies in recent years.(Figure 2,3)

(Figure 2)

Figure 3

- volumetric region of interest performed on three-dimensional (3D) images.
- Digital template on the noninjured side (gray) superimposed
- Face and axial view of the final CT resulting in asymmetric positioning of the bone.⁽⁹⁾

Discussion

The current manufacturing process for implants customized for each patient takes several days to finish. It is anticipated that the production time for fabricating these implants will decrease and become more cost-effective with the introduction of newer 3D printing technology. Currently, a number of oral and maxillofacial surgery specialties, such as orthognathic surgery, maxillofacial skeleton reconstruction, and temporomandibular joint (TMJ) complete joint replacement, use PSIs.⁽¹⁰⁾

PSI as TMJ Joint Replacement

Temporomandibular joint (TMJ) is often affected by a wide spectrum of disorders, including extra articular and intra articular pathologies. These have to be treated by simultaneously removing the lesion and joint together, with primary joint reconstruction to restore its anatomic structure and function as much as possible. Total TMJ prosthesis is an effective and reliable method of joint reconstruction. Total allo plastic TMJ prosthesis is one of the effective and efficient methods of joint reconstruction. However, there is still an urgent need to design a new TMJ prosthesis because of no commercially available TMJ prosthesis appropriate for the clinical application.(Figure 4)⁽¹¹⁾

(Figure 4)

Reconstruction of Maxillofacial Skeleton

Technically possible, highly accurate, and linked to low rates of plate related complications and a strong likelihood of bone healing in the osteotomy gaps, fibula free flap fixation using patient-specific 3D-printed mini plates is a viable choice. (Figure 5)

(Figure 5)

Workflow demonstration for CAD/CAM: Cutting and drilling guides positioned at the fibula segments (green and blue) and the mandible defect (orange). Both permanent and temporary holes are provided in the guides for the purpose of fixing miniplates. Bottom left: Dental setup of the lower dentition (pink) and visualisation of the upper jaw dentition (violet) for the purpose of implant insertion planning. Also displayed are osteotomy lines 1, 2, and 3. The bottom right corner displays the final reconstructive outcomes using 3D-printed miniplates customised for each patient.⁽¹²⁾

PSI in Reconstruction of Orbital Floor and Wall Fractures

With PSIs, ocular fractures can be precisely reconstructed thanks to a comprehensive digital workflow. Transferring the coordinate system from the planning programme to the production software is a prerequisite for the digital process in order to prevent the virtual implant from being placed incorrectly and laboriously. Despite the fact that PSI are dimensionally more

stable than manually bent titanium implants, a circumferential cushion is nevertheless advised. Moreover, PSI rigidity inhibits implant deformation during implantation.(Figure 6)^(13,14)

(Figure 6)

PSI in Treatment of Mandibular Fractures

Oral and maxillofacial surgeons treat maxillofacial injuries most frequently. Owing to its elasticity like bone, PEEK could be a good substitute material. The use of (PEEK) material for cranio maxillofacial reconstructions has gained recognition in recent years. At six months, follow-up radiological and clinical findings from the fixation of a mandibular fracture with a specially designed PEEK plate are satisfactory.(Figure 7)⁽¹⁵⁾

(Figure 7)

PSI in Orthognathic Surgery

The development of CAD/CAM technology and 3D imaging has completely changed orthognathic surgery. The potential mistakes resulting from autorotation of the mandible were removed by this procedure; however, the final maxillary position was fixed using the more traditional method of intraoperative plate bending, which is technique-sensitive and prone to error. For correction of this plates are first planned, then the holes are prepared and the final PSI plate is inserted after a post-guided osteotomy (Figure 8)⁽¹⁰⁾

(Figure 8)

Conclusion

Oral and maxillofacial surgery's response to personalised medicine is patient-specific implants. When compared to manually bent titanium mesh implants, PSIs are a more accurate and straightforward reconstruction option. Automation makes it possible to implement time and safety efficient daily procedures; as such, its use ought to be promoted. Any surgeon can readily plan an implant; it doesn't require specialised knowledge of certain software. The World Health Organisation has previously said that by 2020, PSIs should be a major part of daily activities and should eventually replace conventional implants. This industry will continue to develop as a result of advancements in CAD/CAM technology and falling costs, which will enhance accuracy, efficiency, and overall results.

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